

THE INFLUENCE OF ANCIENT CHINESE MYTHS ON THE TRADITIONAL VIEW OF DEATH

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Annotation. *In China, many ancient myths reflect the primitive people's consciousness of life and death, and the concept of death of primitive people has similarities with the subsequent traditional death viewpoint. The research on the death view in ancient Chinese mythology is mainly to explore the death view contained in the myth itself, and the reasons behind these views. But few researchers compared it with the traditional death view. From recognizing death to seeking resistance, people keep achieving their value during this long process, minimize the impact of death on each one's spirit, and achieve immortality and eternity, all the actions in this process are inspirations given to modern people. This paper analyzes the ancient mythology death view and explores the inheritance of the traditional view of death. The ancient mythological death view and the Chinese traditional death view have similarities in the understanding of life and death, and the realization of immortality. Simultaneously, this study fills the gaps in the existing study for the impact of ancient myths on the traditional view of death. By drawing parallels between the conventional and mythological conceptions of death, we seek to establish a link between traditional and ancient civilization. By exploring the practice and psychological activities of the Chinese nation in its childhood, as well as the potential power and inertia of the Chinese nation, it is expected that a connection between traditional civilization and ancient civilization will be further unraveled. The cultural roots of Chinese people's attitude towards death from ancient myths will be subjected to further analysis.*

Key Words: *ancient mythology; view of death; cultural values; China; immortality*

1. Introduction

As the expressive form of the ancestors' wisdom, myth is understood as representing the genes of culture. The subsequent branches combined, including literature, history, and philosophy cannot cover all concepts that myth implied. Myth,

the divine narration, coexists with prehistorically religious beliefs, ritual activities, and acts as the joint source for literature, history, and philosophy [1]. The myths of the ancient world still resonate in contemporary minds; mythic figures and the stories that describe them still speak to us, often at a less explicit, at times even subconscious, level [2]. Myths are seen by many as an optimal vehicle for humans to integrate history [3]. At the early stage of ancient Chinese mythology, researchers primarily focused on the mythology itself. The understanding of man and nature, as well as man and society, informed the ancient forefathers' perspectives on everything in the world. Life and death are the most significant contrasts and oppositions that are expressed in this way of thinking through stories.

According to Ernst Cassirer, "the fear of death is undoubtedly one of the most common and deep-rooted human instincts" [4] In recent years, the study of mythology as an educational resource has gradually matured. Chinese mythology is increasingly used in education, and, from a pedagogic point of view, philosophy was applied to the mythology system by a number of researchers. Despite this, the traditional Chinese view of death is mostly centered around the discussion of Taoism, Confucianism, and Buddhism, while researchers rarely discuss the influence of ancient Chinese myths on the traditional view of death.

Ye Shuxian is a researcher who introduced various theories and methods related to mythological studies from other countries. He also applied these theoretical methods to the analysis of Chinese myths [5]. Ye *et al.* [2] critically analyzed mythology from a philosophical perspective and constructed the mythological universe model system of Chinese mythology. The research on the traditional Chinese view of death was often targeted at the life and death discussions from Confucianism, Taoism, and Buddhism. Although it is virtually impossible to quantify the reach and influence of ancient Chinese mythology on the traditional death view but it is evident that considerable knowledge gaps remain. Some efforts were made to compare myths and legends with the Confucian life-death viewpoint and have, consequentially drawn similarities between the two concepts. Both views affirmed that death is manipulated by higher spirits beyond the control of individual consciousness, the two views consider that the operating system has a strong sense of positioning, and embodied the spirit of continuous self-improvement.

1.1 Chinese mythology

The emergence of ancient mythology and Chinese traditional culture went essentially hand in hand, at the same time in history, and, are bound to be inextricably linked [6]. Since mythology can be characterized as a human product with imagination and artistic processing of objective existence in primitive times [7], it has the imaginative advantage to be used as a precious existence for exploring primitive

people's thinking and concepts in different historical eras. To find and lay bare the connection between modern people and those who lived thousands of years ago, we study the remaining part of our ancestors' ideas and the most mysterious essentials of traditional China culture. The ancestors' understanding of life and death was manifested in ancient myths, it had a certain similarity with the Chinese traditional view of death.

As different cultural products in a similar period, ancient mythology, and the three schools of Confucianism, Taoism, and Buddhism overlap conceptually. Death in the myths may be attempted to be immortalized through the conservative powers brought forth by society. Confucius and Lao-Tzu acknowledged that physical life inevitably disappears, but life can be immortal through spiritual means. Confucianism believed that one's deeds can last forever, and human life can transcend physical limits by "setting the virtue, setting the meritorious, and expounding the ideas in writing". The significance of Lao Tzu's legacy is manifested in his interpretation of human existence about transcendent truth, which Lao Tzu regards this as being in harmony with transcendence. Lao Tzu also acknowledges both the finitude of human existence and consistent human efforts to search for infinite divinity and ground of existence. By recognizing the multidimensional aspects of human life, which are comprised of material and spiritual dimensions at every level of existence, he concludes that immortality is intrinsically linked to life [8]. Lao-Tzu put forward the view that "the one who dies without dying can live forever" [9] and that people who are not forgotten after death can live forever.

1.2. Death perception

Death is the limit of life that can not be experienced itself. Like a mathematical limit, the individual gradually moves toward death but never consciously reaches it [10]. In our physical world, it is undisputed that everything can only have one life form. However, in the primitive ages, ancestors wanted to change the life form in the world based on their perceptual knowledge of the world so that the law of life movement could change according to human consciousness [11]. The myth of deformation was the embodiment of this concept. The core of these myths is to replace the objective existence of death with the method of physical change. The concept of death indicated in the mythology of primitive people is that life can be transformed from one thing to another through deformation. The transformed objects can be animals, plants, or even non-life stones. Among certain circles of scholars, there is consensus that life and death are two different stages of the same process, which was surprisingly consistent with Chuang-Tzu's later thesis on death. Chuang-Tzu believed there was no need to separate life and death. In his perception, the two stages belonged to the same process [12]. He even held an extremely open-minded

attitude towards death, thinking that people can enter a more free and happy state, like a princely life after death, which is a continuation of life. Later introduced to China, Buddhism also believed that life and death are the processes of reincarnation [13]. Even though it is generally acknowledged that death is a normal part of existence, the Chinese have developed a distinctive perspective on death and dying as a result of this integration. The populace derives a substantial definition of death and dying from this. Life thus is the reincarnation in this process, and life and death are the nodes of entering different worlds. None of these assertions considered that death means eternal disappearance without existence.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the present research. Section 3 expounds on the concern of primitive humans about death and how they struggled after recognizing death. Section 4 discusses the consciousness of life transformation. Records of death-life transformation in ancient myths are standard, while the remarkable thing is that death-life transformation echoes in Chuang-Tzu and Buddhism's perceptions of death. In section 5, we focus on the value of death, analyze the pursuit of eternal, and the accomplishment of life immortality in traditional culture on the premise of acknowledging the inevitable fact of death. Section 6 concludes the life-death transition and immortality, inherited and developed in the traditional view of death, and puts forward future work on how contemporary Chinese people inherit and develop these traditional views of death.

2. Conceptualized context

Adopting the method of “grasp of the original ecology” [14], this study is mainly centered around a multi-disciplinary holistic research frame, aiming to grasp the original *ecology* of history, and collect more contemporary situations of history to be interpreted. This paper explores the methods of comparison and psychoanalytic analysis from multiple perspectives, such as literary anthropology, philology, psychology, and sociology, but not exclusively, as a means to acknowledge the many facets of how to understand the ancient concept of death in China. The paper firsts analyze ancestral views of death through ancient mythology. Then we conceptualize and explore the life transformation and interpret immortality after death in mythology and traditional death view.

2.1 Ancient Chinese myths

In China, the most rudimentary yet well-known ancient myths, the so-called broad myths, refer to the myths and legends before the Xia Dynasty, traced back to ancient times, whereas the narrow sense of ancient myths refers to the myths from the Xia Dynasty to the Han Dynasty. This paper acknowledges and adopts the broad definition of ancient mythology that was created by primitive people in social practice. It expresses ancient people's fundamental understanding and desire for

nature and social phenomena in the form of stories, and values methodological and functional story telling, often passed on orally or in written form. It is “the natural and social form itself processed in an unconscious artistic way through the fantasy of the people” [16]. To be sure, the study of ancient Chinese myths mainly involves four central aspects:

First, the research on the myth itself represented by Yuan *et al.* [8]. These types of works have frequently been subjected to collecting, sorting, annotating, and compiling among the scattered and fragmentary materials of ancient myths, and compiled the encyclopedia-like set of influential works of ancient myths in plain language. His work presents readers with a rich and immersive world, it vividly describes the social life of ancient Chinese.

Second, mythology is also used as an educational resource in daily education and teaching activities. Some of the ancient myths involved in research usually are myths that are orally passed on from one generation to the next, which is why the retention of the ancestors' thinking in the original myths is relatively weak. Zhang *et al.* [17] found a different interpretation of modern society and education after, in their eyes, attention to mythical phenomena essentially became obsolete, after which they examined modern society and modern education in which myths lost the appeal they held previously. The scholars analyzed the possibility and basis of the myth's reappearance in contemporary society and also expounded the theoretical basis of mythology as an educational resource from four varying aspects: 1) Mythology is a way for the human to grasp and make sense of the world, 2) Mythology reflects the ultimate care for the human, 3) Mythology is a near-indispensable cultural force, and 4) Mythology reflects the everyday psychological needs of the human, it demonstrates. Liu *et al.* [18] summed up the mythology paradigms from the education perspective, which generally includes three aspects of educational content: a rich view of the world, life, and value; rich national ethos; and simple ethics and morality. From an educational perspective, myths most prominently echo with children (and to some extent, children attribute special meaning to myths). Liu *et al.* [18] analyzed the implementation of mythology in children's education mainly through Chinese courses and other methods, such as ideological and moral courses, storytelling, etc.

Third, the introduction of foreign theoretical methods related to mythology research. Ye *et al.* [6] systematically explored Chinese mythology's philosophical implications, models, and other related issues. He explored the mythological foundation of Chinese-style thinking through mythology and the all-encompassing "meta-language" of mythological philosophy. He disclosed the mystery behind the four faces of the Emperor Mingtang and the Yellow Emperor, explored Chaos's seven

bleeding orifices and the view of seven-day creation, the creation of the earth and the origin of the appearance of "Shenzhou," and created a mythical cosmology.

Fourth, some researchers conducted comparative analyses between ancient Chinese and ancient Greek mythology and explored the similarities, differences, and reasons behind them. Lin *et al.* [19] mentioned that Western mythology found its way to China at the end of the nineteenth century. In the early twentieth century, under the inspiration of Western anthropology and mythology, Chinese mythology consciousness began to be awakened, with pioneers starting to explore and establish Chinese mythology locally. For more than a century, the "Comparative Study of Chinese and Greek Mythology" has been an essential theme of Chinese mythology research. With the world's cultural landscape changing since the 1980s, "China and the West" have become a significant cultural relationship. The "Comparative Study of Chinese and Greek Mythology" has also entered a new stage.

2.2 Traditional death view

Most of the research on the traditional view of death focused on understanding Confucianism, Buddhism, and Taoism, especially the views of life and death by Confucianism and Taoism. Li *et al.* [20] analyzed the attitudes of Confucius, Lao-Tzu, Chuang-Tzu, Taoism, and Buddhism towards life and death. Xu *et al.* [21] believed that both Lao-Tzu and Chuang-tzu emphasized the inevitability of death, but Lao-Tzu regarded death as a negative state. At the same time, Chuang-Tzu held a philosophical and happy attitude. Chuang-Tzu deemed life and death to belong to the same process. Ma *et al.* [22] believed life had been the most cherished existence in Chinese culture since ancient times.

When facing death, people show complex anxiety emotions and search for various resolution strategies to face them. The best way is to adhere to the laws of nature and face them calmly. Peng *et al.* [23] divided the traditional view of life and death into rational and irrational in "The Analysis of Traditional Chinese Views on Life and Death." Zhou *et al.* [24] believed that achieving the state of life immortality is the ultimate goal of humankind. Both Chinese mythology and Greek mythology ascertain the ancestors' knowledge and understanding process of death. People constantly attempted to escape death as their initial understanding developed from puzzlement to fear. The ancient Chinese and Greek people overcame the fear of death and demonstrated human power through different, incomprehensible ways, previously unimaginable, and thereby achieving spiritual immortality and eternity.

2.3 Relationship between ancient myths and death view

This part focuses on two aspects. One is the study of the ancestors' view of life and death reflected in mythology, and the other is to compare the view of life and

death in ancient mythology and the view of life and death in traditional thoughts such as Confucianism and Taoism. Wang *et al.* [25] explored the life consciousness of primitive humans and the cultural psychology of the life-death view through ancient myths and primitive customs. He believed that primitive humans assimilated human life consciousness into the pattern of natural changes, resulting in psychology beyond death and a series of related activities. There are four fundamental ways for primitive people to overcome death:

1. To plan a resurrection after death
2. To overcome individual death with totem continuation and resurrection through descendants
3. To interpret death as a transformative process
4. To reach immortality and reincarnation of the soul

Wang *et al.* [26] held that “the transformation from snake to fish” in the text “Zhuan Xu’s re-birth through death” in The Classic of Mountains and Seas is notable. Snake and fish, which all belong to Yin (negatively associated), represent the meaning of “life continuation.” “Snake,” with the characteristics of mystery, lethality, and reproduction, represents “death and regeneration,” and “Fish,” with a solid ability to reproduce, signifies “re-birth.” He concluded that this kind of transformation in myths showed primitive people’s initial understanding of life and death, who used metaphors to show this understanding. Struggle with death was displayed through “the immortal soul,” “the changeable form,” and “the alternation of life and death.” Li *et al.* [20] persisted that the primitive view of death is consistent with Lao-Tzu’s view that death and life are two interrelated stages in the same process. Lao-Tzu mentioned the process from life to death, but whether he believed that life and death are two process stages remains to be verified. Zhao Fan *et al.* [7], in “See the Confucian View from Myths and Legends,” elaborated on two discourses of similar times. Zhao believed that the two have similarities in terms of the power that governs life and death, the sense of position for life, and the spirit of continuous self-improvement.

3. Ancient people’s perspectives about death and its inevitability

In ancient times, people cherished the notion, and firmly realized, how death, through elementary survival pressure, was brought about by the natural environment and then-defined elements in their direct surroundings. Based on the observation of natural phenomena, such as the withering and blooming of plants and trees, the cyclical alternations of day and night, coupled with the psychology of avoidance of death, ancestral rites came to the death-resurrection method of fighting death [25], regularly recorded in myths.

3.1 Great survival pressure in a natural environment

Due to the natural environment, living conditions, and other factors, humans then faced a colossal threat of death, often caused by a lifelong reality of struggle and survival. Various factors that seem not to be a threat in modern times can cause the ancestors' death [27]. The records of *The Huainanzi: Surveying Obscurities* (Lan Ming Xun) reveal the harsh living conditions of the people at the time:

"In ancient times, the four ends of the earth collapsed, and the earth sunk. The sky could not cover all the earth, and the earth could not fully carry all things. The non-extinguished fire was wide and fierce, and the vast and boundless flood did not disappear. The ferocious beasts devoured the kind people, and the fierce birds grabbed the old and the weak by their claws [28]."

While tasting and experiencing the joy of survival, the people also continued to witness the nearness of fear and confusion, tightly entangled with each other. The book agrees on the overall valuing of cosmology, its *de* or potency, and common self-cultivation techniques, there is however less common understanding the practical interpretations of these concepts.

3.2 Primitive people's conceptual understanding of death

In conceptual terms, death is complex to acquire, and even after succeeding, it will be a rare cognitive feature once it moves wholly past the human species [29]. The word "death" was written in oracle bone inscriptions, and Shang Chengzuo characterizes the depicted scene insofar that one can distinguish "a person worshipping beside a pile of decayed bones." This observation indicates that primitive civilizations or organized communities have the notion of a bone cult [30]. While the physical (and even the spiritual, under certain circumstances) body disappears after death, as the rationale that scholars hold on to, bones have the advantage of being able to remain, survive even, for a long time. They followed the long-held belief that bones are proof of actual life existing in another form. *An Etymological Dictionary of Ancient Chinese Bronze Inscription* edited by Zhou Fagao collected various scholars' interpretations of the word "death." It has two meanings: the first is "corpse," which is the object of sacrifice, whereas the second is "permanent" [30].

The word "death" interpretation is similar to the ancestors' understanding of death. Materially, "death" manifests itself as being mere dry bones. The premise is that, in essence, the soul does not know where to return after death, but the bones continue to exist for a long time, just as life still exists. This aspect is also known as a non-animal life concept. Wang Zhongling believed that the impact of non-animal life concepts on

people's life concepts leads to the expectations of death and rebirth or resurrection [25], which comes from the ancestors' observation and the analogy of things in nature. As abstract thinking has not yet developed, analogical thinking has dominated people's understanding of the physical world. They observed the world, saw the changes between winter and summer, and the alternation of day and night. They saw vegetation withering and prospering and tides ebbing and flowing. These natural phenomena constantly in reincarnation also meet the urgent expectations of human beings for death and rebirth, giving those who have not yet developed rational thinking a simple and "reasonable" explanation. The logic of nature becomes applied to people's understanding of life and death. As a result, the ancestors believed that human life is also in the cycle of death and resurrection, just like the seasons and time. The moment of death is not the end of life but an entry to a new derivative form [31]. It is the inevitable process of "life" and a step in the cycle of reincarnation, like the moon rains or shines. "Death" is the new "life." Only when life completes its inevitable reincarnation, it can return to reality in other forms through death. This death-resurrection method is also a simple method that the ancestors thought about to overcome death. Ancestors acknowledged that "death" is only the deformation of "life" and is the inevitable process of developing to another form.

Spiritually, "death" is a concept of time, which is eternal. Death is not the end of life, but the transformation of the specific form of life can be permanent through the transformation of life. "Death" is a passing ritual through which people can enter another phase of life. However, the living cannot experience death. Initially, people were afraid of such a mysterious process and instinctively tended to avoid it.

3.3 Ancestors' thinking on the cause of death

Primitive people did not have the consciousness of death at the beginning. Because of the complicated process of the birth of life, they only knew about life without death. The ancestors gradually felt the pain caused by the sudden death of relatives and friends in production. They felt the fear of the unknown world after death, as is explicitly mentioned in the "Son of Elephants" of the Dulong ethnic group living in Yunnan province, China, that people never die. It is only because of a little mistake that the fate of mankind has been so sadly reversed [28]. According to this description, we can find that the ancestors have already tried to explain the cause of death. They gradually realized that death is inevitable (it is not possible to put off death indefinitely) and unpredictable (the exact timing of death cannot be unknown) [29]. Out of their ignorance of death, the death of one individual in their companions often causes great psychological panic among other members, and they think that mysterious supernatural forces influence death [24]. For this reason, they began to worship ghosts and gods (the sacrificial rituals and methods in ancient myths also

claim).

3.4 Overcoming death in ancient times

The ancestors knew death and the inevitability of it but did not know the true meaning of death, so they hoped to transcend and overcome it. The search of a good existence ultimately leads individuals to immortality. The myths were created by our primitive ancestors as a solution to their thinking issues and as a way to communicate their search of spirituality in order to escape the reality of death. According to the death-resurrection method, the ancestors converted human life into another animate or non-living body. According to *Sui Chao Zi*, Yu's wife, Tu Shan, saw that Yu resurfaced and assumed the role of flood control, materializing in the form of a bear. She felt guilty and changed into a rock under Mount Song in Henan [30]. Stones are inanimate, but it was animate and even had children in this methodology. The other way is resurrection directly through death, divided into two kinds. One is that the body will transform Xingtian: Xingtian was beheaded as a punishment after opposing the Emperor, but despite the beheading, he demonstrated a unique occurrence of resurrection. Writings illustrate how "after his breasts turned into eyes and belly button into the mouth, and he continued to fight with his hand waving a shield and axe" [31]. The second element entails that the body will not undergo any transformation". *The Classic of Mountains and Seas: The Classic of Regions Beyond the North Seas* recorded that in the Wuqi Kingdom, the men and women lived by eating mud and were buried when they died. Their hearts would not rot, and they would resurrect 120 years after death [32]. These now seemingly absurd stories are the records of the original human struggling against death.

4. Consciousness of life transformation

In essence, ancestors believed that life and death belong to the same process and can be interchanged. Chuang-Tzu, the representative of Taoism, put forward this view of life and death transformation many times in "The Great Master (Da Zong Shi)". Similar to the mythical view of death, he upheld the conviction that there is no need to artificially separate the boundaries of life and death, and even death can make people freer. Buddhism later absorbed this critical insight in "Samsara", which also reflects the similarity to the mythical view of death.

4.1 Life transformation in myths

Ancient mythology recorded many transformations between different life forms. The reason for these myths firstly lies in the ancestors' concept of animatism (the belief that everything, including living and non-living, possesses an impersonal, supernatural life force that has an impact on people and events). Under the conditions of cognition at the time, the ancestors could not distinguish the subject of thinking from the natural world. They believed that all existences in the world are alive in

different forms, and the essence of life is the same. The second is the consciousness that life can be transformed and continued. In such myths, the transformation of form is essentially the transformation of life. Transformation is only the change of form, with the essence of life not changed during the transformation.

The Classic of the Great Wilderness: West recorded Zhuanxu's death and re-birth. It is said that when the strong northern wind blew, the underground spring water splashed over the ground. At this time, the story goes, the snake turned into a fish, and the dead Zhuanxu transformed his soul into the fish, becoming a female fish with a half-human body [35]. *The Classic of the Mountains: North* recorded that Yan Di's daughter Nu Wa went to the East China Sea and was drowned in the sea. Her soul became a Jingwei bird. This bird "looks like a crow with a pattern on its head and red feet and was named Jingwei" [35]. In *Records of Huayang Kingdom: The Kingdom of Shu*, Emperor Wang turned into a cuckoo [35]. Humanized animals are a way of life-to-death transformation in primitive human concepts. This also shows that death is not the end of life, but an inevitable node in the process of life transformation.

4.2 *Chuang-Tzu's Concept of Life and Death Conversion*

Chuang-Tzu held that escaping death is not necessary. Life and death are two stages of a process, not two extreme sides. The two are not entirely different, and there is no need to separate death from this process [10]. In the cause of death in myths, a similar situation applies. "The Great Master" expressed that life and death are the parts of the body forming a whole, and there is no need to separate them and artificially make death a fearful process [18]. Regarding this view, he praised Meng Sun's attitude toward the death of his mother. Meng Sun did not distinguish between life and death. He denied that life and death were the sequential starting and ending points but saw them as a "transformation" process with no end [11]. In this process, life and death interchange with each other cyclically. There is no clear boundary between life and death.

The essence of Chuang-Tzu's acceptance of death is to set death as another form of life. In "The Great Master," Chuang-Tzu believed that people escape the fatigue and difficulty of life through death and have a permanent rest [12]. The story of skeletons in "Zhi Le" proposed that death can free people from the suppression of strict hierarchy, the hustle and bustle of the year, and the limits of work and life, to achieve a desirable princely state [12]. Chuang-Tzu's non-avoidance attitude toward death is because that death is a more abundant and carefree life. Death is not a process that one should attempt to avoid, but rather the start of a transformation into a better life.

4.3 *Samsara in Buddhism*

Since Buddhism's introduction to China in the Han Dynasty, it has gradually been

localized and has become an essential part of traditional Chinese thought. The concept of samsara in Buddhism still strongly influences people's more attuned and modern views of life-death in China. Consistent with the transition between life and death, as depicted in myths, Buddhism believes that life and death are different stages in an infinite cycle ("samsara") and interchange when deemed opportune. The fundamental difference is that Buddhism believes that this is an inevitable conversion of existing conditions. The realization of this radical conversion is a given, but the eventually converted form depends on people's behavior during life itself. Compared with the unconditional life-death conversion in the ancient myths, Buddhism emphasized that whichever form of behavior in the real world determines whether people enter the pure and promised land (heaven) or the eerie and terrifying avici (hell). This view of the after-death world has not been mentioned in the previous discourses in Chinese culture [19]. The lifelike reality of the world after death conditioned people's behavior in real life.

5. Immortality of life

In Chinese myths, individuals will continue to achieve their value in other ways after death and make life eternal through this value. Immortality is a concept that is reflected in Confucius, Lao-Tzu, and Taoism's view of death. Confucius believed that spiritual life is more lasting and important than physical life, and Lao-Tzu argued that "the one who died and was unforgotten can live forever". This pursuit of immortality in ancient mythology was also vividly demonstrated in Taoism, it also showed in the royal and aristocratic classes.

5.1 Eternal life through death in mythology

Death makes people realize the finiteness of life and arouses a sense of fear. Sociality facilitates the emergence of solid social attachments that are unlikely to vanish with death [35]. Therefore, another way to face death is to give death social value [21]. On an abstract level, passing away forever does not mean disappearing forever. Individuals can continue to conserve society through their values. According to ancient writing, Pan Gu created the world and fell, his breath turned into wind and clouds, his voice into thunder, his left eye into the sun, and his right eye into the moon. His limbs formed four pillars supporting the sky, his five internal organs took the shape of five mountains, and the blood became the rivers nourishing the world. His veins reappeared as mountains and roads, and his muscle skin functioned the farmland and soil. His hair and mustaches were stars, his fine hairs became vegetation, and the teeth and bones became metal minerals and stones. His bone marrow turned into pearls and jewels, and the sweat into rain and dew, moisturizing everything. Even tiny insects on his body were morphed by the wind and became the

people living on earth [7]. Death is unacceptable and inevitable, while death is also a way that personal values can be embraced and carried out.

Nv Wa, another goddess for creating the world, repaired the sky and the earth after destruction. She dredged rivers, fought against beasts, controlled the floods with reed ash, and recovered the world at peace [25]. *The Classic of the Great Wilderness*: West mentioned that “ten gods were transformed from Nv Wa’s intestine, who lived in the wild of Li Guang and blocked the road” [32]. No more explanation about how Nuwa’s intestines became gods was listed. Yuan Ke (Yuan Shengshi) cautiously speculated in *Explanation of Ancient Myths* that Nuwa incarnated like Pan Gu after death, with her intestines transforming into ten gods [34]. Nv Wa has already contributed enormously to the world during her lifetime. Her body continuously benefited humankind after she died. The spirit of sacrifice for the sake of others has been encouraged from ancient times till now. After her death, her body continued to serve the community. This value of collective sacrifice has received substantial praise in mainstream Chinese values since ancient times.

The Classic of the Mountains: Central recorded Tian Di’s daughter Nushi. Nushi died in Guyao Mountain and turned into jade-like flowers named Yao grass. The leaves of this grass overlap each other, and the flowers are said to be yellow. People attribute aphrodisiac powers to it when consumed [35]. All these social values are visible. Protagonists continued to exert their values through death. As the ancestors rationalized their understanding of death, this substantive value in mythology gradually evolves into spiritual ones in the later concept of death.

5.2 Immortality

Confucianism, a system of thought with the most profound effect on Chinese culture, believes that life is the most precious thing between heaven and earth; life and death are the products of the universe, and death is inevitable. Confucius said: "All living creatures must die and return to the soil after death" [35]. Nevertheless, under certain conditions, people can be immortal. Confucius continued by stating that: "People with lofty ideals won't give up benevolence to survive but are willing to sacrifice for benevolence [36]." Similarly, *Zuozhuan*, China's first great recorded work of history and literature, describes that "the highest goal in life is to establish virtue, secondly to establish meritorious deeds, and thirdly to establish a school. Any of the three will not be abolished for a long time, as this is called immortality [37]." "*Benevolence*" and "*Three establishments*" are standards set for people. Once reaching these standards, people can pass on their deeds to later generations and reach an immortal state of symbiosis with the heavens and the earth, and the sun and the moon.

According to *The Overall Guideline* of Xunzi, after listening to Confucius, Zi Gong said, "The man of high character finally can have a rest, and the villain also stop wrongdoing [38]." In *Tan Gong, The Book of Rites*, Zi Zhang, in a progressed state of illness, voiced to Shen Xiang: "The man of high character departs, and the villain just dies [39]." In other words, the villain's death disappeared physically, and all traces of his existence in the world with it. The death of a man of high character means, conversely, that the activities that his deeds need his body have ceased, but the influence of his previous deeds remains to exist, and thereby affecting the world and reaching a state of immortality. The scholar Hu Hong of the Southern Song Dynasty arguably attributed to the debate about "immortality" in *Zhi Yan* by stating that "if people do not regard their body and life as being private, and strive to make themselves public in the world, then nothing in this world does belong to me. The religious term refers to the human spirit. An individual's life can also be continued in other people or objects, and a person can achieve eternal life in this way [40]. The same may apply to the many myths mentioned above, such as the notion that human life goes on in the form of another individual or object. However, as these studies have shown, ancestors who lived in these earlier times, under different circumstances, did not pursue their spiritual needs actively according to these norms.

5.3 Un-forgotten people lives in longevity

Chapter 50 of *Lao-tse* stated that "the life process of human beings is firstly in a stage closer to birth, then is prime of life, after that, everyone continues to grow older, finally getting into death. The growth and development stage account for three out of ten, and another three in ten is the aging and death stage [10]" This world-renowned piece affirms physical death but believes there are more critical existences than physical life. In Chapter 33 of *Lao-tse*, "The one who died but was un-forgotten lives in longevity [10]" was mentioned. As for the Chinese interpretation of "wang," the author believes that the silk book of Lao-tse, unearthed in Mawangdui, Hunan province, can be used as a reference. In this book, the verb "wang" in Chinese is interpreted as "forget," implying that people who died and were not forgotten live in longevity. This statement is similar to the Confucian argument of "immortality," and an active response to the helplessness of seeing life passing away.

5.4 The pursuit of immortality

There are many myths about immortality in ancient myths. Either a particular citizen can live forever or can live for a thousand years. The spiritual connotation is that they are all born out of fear of death. In *The Classic of Mountains and Seas: The Classic of Regions Within the West Seas*, it recorded that to the east of the sacred beast Kaiming, there are genius doctors, such as Wu Peng, Wu Di, Wu Yang, Wu Lu, Wu Fan, and Wu Xiang. They sat around Ya Yu, a god who was killed by a courtier,

with a human face and a snake body. These genius doctors held the immortal medicine in their hands, hoping to resist death [35]. In *Huainanzi*, a section describes how Hou Yi got the immortal medicine from Empress of Heaven Wangmu, while his wife Chang E stole and took the medicines.

Moreover, finally, she flew to the moon [27]. Nowadays, the effect of magic medicine has still existed. In today's vast rural areas of China, older generations still go to temples to ask for an amulet. The psychic people write specific words and patterns with a brush dipped in a mixture of new red cinnabar on yellow paper. People who ask for it should take it home, burn it to ashes, mix it with wine or water and then drink it. In this way, people believed that amulets could cure. They believe those who drink it can eliminate evil and keep the body healthy. In addition to the elixir, some foods can last forever after eating.

According to *The Classic of Mountains and Seas: The Classic of the Great Wilderness: West*, there is an immortal country whose nationals have the surname, Ah, and they eat Ganmu, a tree never dies [34]. The categories of Product of *Natural History* recorded, "The shrine is in the high stone marshes, there are immortals, and rich in Nyingchi, and springs. Once drinking it, people will awake after three hundred years and become immortal." "In Yuanqiu Mountain, there are undead trees. Eating it can have longevity. There are red springs, and drinking it will never get old [43]." In addition to eating and drinking, there is also a kind of immortal human being. There is a saying in *The Classic of Mountains and Seas* that "immortal people" lived in the east, were black in appearance, and had longevity [34]." This view of death also affects people's views on death in the future. Immortal medicine is a miraculous plant. To be undead is ancient China's eternal pursuit of life, especially for the relatively wealthy and prosperous scholar-official class, whose desire for it is especially strong.

Although Lao Tzu admits the existence of death, he also hopes to achieve a state full of vitality like a baby through monasticism so that he can stay away from death like a baby [9]. Taoism put forward the "immortality" view of death. The "immortality" view has had far-reaching implications on the traditional Chinese view of death, especially for the aristocracy. This view has an efficient impact in the following hundred years. As the founder of immortal Taoism theory and rituals, Ge Hong theoretically proved the existence of Hsien (immortals) and the possibility of immortality. In this discourse, the primitive understanding of Hsien-immortality functions as a diverging organizing principle that orders the manner in which he experiences the social and cultural world, as a rather ideological resolution for experienced feelings of incongruence between outer reality and inner world, and, consequently, as a soteriological vision of an alternate version of ideal self-identity, seen in contrast to the Han idealized Confucian sage. He expounded on specific

methods of becoming immortal from the aspect of rituals, such as nourishing qi, alchemy, and medicine. Emperor Qin, Emperor Wu of the Han Dynasty, and some scholar-officials in the Warring States and Qin-Han period tried various methods to stay immortal. The construction of Taoist discourse of Hsien-identity, instanced in Ge Hong's works [43], should, therefore, not merely be seen as something abstract and arbitrary without the roots in socio-cultural reality, but, instead, a new formation and shape that altered generations' thinking about life, death, and the conception of immortality. Whether it is the everlasting kingdom in myths or the belief in the methods to keep immortal in reality, it is a response that people born out of fear of the irresistible force of death and the unknown world after death.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

This paper explores the intrinsic relationship between ancient Chinese myths and the traditional conception of death, traces and weighs the process of the ancestors' attention to death, and analyses the corresponding solutions based on it. Views of the transition between death and life and immortality in myths suggest a symbiosis inherited and developed from the traditional view of death. This paper contributes to the discussion on the evaluation and appreciation of death inheritance and the imbeddedness in the more conventional analytical methods to understand myths. It is imperative to direct this discipline in such a way that it allows the application of multidisciplinary interpretation of myths and (abstract) concepts such as life, death and eternity. The ancestors attributed social value and a certain weight to death in myths. Both Confucius and Lao Tzu believed that people's words and deeds during their lives determine the length of their spiritual life. The premise of the immortality of physical and spiritual life is to maximize one's value to society. How these traditional views of death have been inherited and changed later, and how they will affect the Chinese people today remains to be considered. This allows for further investigation to advance this discipline's overall body of knowledge on ancient cultural and mythical concepts in China.

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